

100 Households, 100 Circular Stories: Inspiring Sustainable Living in Europe

Deliverable 3.1: Methodological framework of LCA for impact assessment of behaviour change

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D3.1 Methodological Framework LCA

Work package	WP3 - Development of digital platform and impact assessment measures
Lead Beneficiary	NOVA ID
Responsible Author(s)	Julian Mast (Hochschule Ruhr West)
Report description	The document shows the development of the methodological framework to assess the environmental impact saving of the behaviour changes and challenges developed within WP2 by applying Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). Furthermore, it shows links and interconnections to the CircleUp app concept.

Revision History

Version #	Implemented by	Revision Date	Description of changes
1.0	Julian Mast	14/10	Original version
Review	Ritvars Freimanis	17/10	- tone of the document expresses criticism to project; - lack of data for ITEMS list (mismatch of units for CO2 data and source references) - Lack of Coherence with D2.1. but mainly this problem arises from D2.1. being inconsistent
1.1	Julian Mast	28/10	Cross-check with D2.1 in order to be coherent with D2.1 addition of conversion factors and sources for EI factors

Approval Procedure

Version #	Deliverable Name	Approved by	Institution	Approval Date

List of abbreviations

LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
EI	environmental impact

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of work package 3.2 is to present the environmental effects saved as a result of behavioural changes in the project households, which they achieve through certain challenges (cf. D2.1).

The savings in households can cover many different material flows, as the domains of packaging, textiles, electronics and especially food contain many different products that also have different impacts on the environment.

Deliverable 3.1 provides a method for selecting the most significant material flows from the four domains described above and subsequently developing a method for quantifying the material flows with as little effort as possible for households by using the framework of the CircleUp app. The corresponding objective is to collect a sufficient amount of data within a reasonable time frame for households in order to then use LCA modelling to determine how high the savings were for the various households.

The main parts of this work include i) identification of the most significant material flows in the four domains. Significance itself is determined on the one hand by the expected amounts of savings. On the other hand, it is determined by the expected magnitude of environmental savings per unit of reference; ii) development of an app-based method for the precise quantification of material flows, taking into account the time spent by households should be as minimal as possible; iii) development of the LCA modelling scope for work package 5. This contains e.g. country-specific differences or differences in manufacturing within a product group.

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1. Introduction and Overview

The CircleUp project aims to increasingly promote CE practices in households by using psychological interventions to encourage a change in thinking on a micro level. While psychology identifies how and why individuals adopt more sustainable habits, other methods such as life cycle thinking are better suited to demonstrating the effect this has in terms of reduced material flows (or in other words: the savings of the households) and their respective reduction of environmental impacts. LCA provides the objective framework to quantify the actual ecological impact of these behavioural choices in two ways: 1) material flow reductions, 2) environmental impact reductions.

The deliverable demonstrates how to develop a method that makes it possible to track the defined behaviours and challenges, quantify the savings achieved in households, and demonstrate how the environmental impact of these savings can be calculated. The latter element will then be made accessible and assessable within the course of processing work package 5.

By integrating LCA into the context of the CircleUp project, interventions can be directed toward behaviours that yield the greatest real-world ecological gains, ensuring that psychological effectiveness aligns with environmental relevance.

Chapter two of this document describes the goal and scope of the environmental impact assessment within the CircleUp project. Chapter three describes the behavioural changes and how they affect households' resource flows. The fourth chapter describes how the material flows that are to be tracked and quantified during the course of the project are to be determined. These are divided according to the four domains. Chapter five describes how data should be collected within the CircleUp app. The data reflects the savings achieved through the various challenges and is presented as material flows.

The due date of this publication is in month 22 of the project. After the publication within D3.1, this document can be further adapted and updated until the end of the project (M42) as implementing a LCA-modelling in impact assessment is an iterative process. However, after the end of the work package in month 23, the core of the method development will no longer be subject to significant changes.

2. Goal and Scope of environmental impact assessment

Within the project, LCA assesses to which extent psychologically-based interventions can encourage households to reduce their environmental impact within the domains of food, packaging, textiles and electronics. From an LCA point of perspective, it is crucial to indicate how many resources households can save by participating in the challenges and to demonstrate the environmental impact that could be avoided by reducing resource flows. Therefore, the LCA approach as part of the assessment will provide two important insights. First, the potential savings of the households will be tracked for each challenge. The underlying assumption here is that the savings can be attributed to the challenge, but in practice it is also possible that other factors could have influenced the change in material flows. They will be in terms of resource flows (i), and second, the environmental impact (EI) of the respective savings will be assessed (ii). The detailed calculation of EI savings will be pursued in WP 5, but households will nevertheless receive an order of magnitude indicating the range of environmental impact savings achieved through the challenges based on literature values. The reduced EI of the respective challenge is the sum of all reduced impacts of the respective products. The reduced EI for each product is calculated from the impact factor per product unit and the quantity of product units saved.

i) As part of each challenge, households are given the mandatory task of reporting their realised savings potential in the app. All material (and energy) flows saved have to be specified and quantified. Using the food domain as an example, it is intended for the households to be able to specify which amount of a certain product could be reduced with respect to a certain challenge. This requires households to enter their savings for each challenge separately via the app. The exact lists and how to enter the realized savings into the app are explained in the following chapters.

ii) To determine the EI of the savings, LCAs are created for each product type and the results are stored in the app. Characterisation factors are used to calculate the contribution of each individual product type to the respective EI of the challenge - e.g. how much global warming potential a particular product unit has (in CO₂-eq). The contributions of all savings are then aggregated to obtain an overall picture of the EI saved. Formula 1 formally shows the EI avoided by reducing resource flows as part of the challenges carried out in households. The variable n represents the products that

are considered, α describes the amount of realized savings within a challenge for each product and β describes the EI per unit of savings of each product.

$$EI = \sum_i^n a_n \cdot \beta_n$$

Formula 1. Calculation of Environmental Impact (EI) of a certain challenge

3. Behaviours and expected changes in resource flows

In the course of D2.1, the following behaviours were defined, which can be divided into the different domains as shown in Table 1. The final behaviours and their associated challenges are included in the further methodological elaboration. Alternative behaviours from D 2.1 are not explicitly mentioned or taken into account.

<i>Domain</i>	<i>Behaviour</i>	<i>Behaviour</i>	<i>Behaviour</i>	<i>Behaviour</i>
Food	Plan purchases to avoid food waste	Reuse leftovers	Give away leftovers	Share your leftover management skills with others
Packaging	Avoid packaging (focus on refuse, reduce)	Reuse packaging	Avoid packaging together	
Textiles	reduce textiles	Buy second hand clothes	Reuse, repair, upcycle clothes	
Electronics	Reduce buying electronics	Repair broken electronics	Reuse electronics	share electronics

Table 1. Domains and respective behaviours provided by D 2.1 (table 23)

It can be expected that the various behaviour changes and the respective challenges will have different effects on the reduction of resource flows. The expected changes in material flows are therefore presented graphically and described in the following subchapters. The way in which the material flows are changed is significantly influencing the modelling of LCA and, as a result, on the collection of the necessary data, and is therefore essential.

3.1 Expected effects on resource flows: food

Within the project, households identify potential savings by using an item list within the app and quantifying their reductions of resource flows. The figures in this chapter illustrate how the savings affect the absolute resource flows. The figures show whether only one household or two households are taken into account in the

modelling, whether additional resource flows are added by the challenge or not, etc. These flows are only intended to illustrate the concept within this chapter and are not included in the calculation itself.

Considering the first behaviour of the domain, the goal is to plan food purchases in advance of buying it in the grocery store. As indicated in Fig. 1, this reduces the total amount of food purchased by individual households. This results in direct savings potential within the same products; substitute products are not required in this context. At the same time, this scenario also reduces the amount of waste generated, as households continue to consume the same effective amount of food (*ceteris paribus*). Fewer purchases therefore result in less waste. In order for the modelling of this scenario to be reasonable and possible within a single data collection, households must be able to estimate what they typically consume and dispose of. The test phase will examine the extent to which this is possible. As part of the feedback from the test phase, households are asked about the reliability of their responses regarding products and quantification. This challenge can therefore only be evaluated in terms of LCA if the household estimates are sufficiently reliable according to households' self-evaluation.

Figure 1. Expected material flow changes: plan purchases to avoid food waste

Fig. 2 also shows the declining amount of necessary material flows in households, which is caused by the reuse of leftovers. This behaviour also results in direct savings potential within the same products and the same household, and no substitute flows are required. Household waste also decreases (*ceteris paribus*). In

this model, households indicate which leftovers they have utilized to supply themselves with food. The amount saved is calculated based on the quantity of products reused, as these did not need to be repurchased.

Figure 2. Expected material flow changes: Reuse leftovers

Fig. 3 shows the behaviour of giving leftovers away. This does not reduce the material flow on the purchasing side in the observed project household. However, passing on leftovers reduces the amount of waste generated by the household. More important, it reduces the need for purchases in third households that receive the leftovers, as these substitute new purchases there. As part of the data collection process, households have to indicate which leftovers they have given to other households. Due to the leftovers substituting primary food purchases in household 2, the amount of waste remains constant and won't increase. The underlying assumption in this case is, that the leftovers have the same quality as primary food purchases so that there is no higher quota of disposal due to ingredients spoiling fastly. In terms of modelling, this scenario extends system boundaries from one household to two households to be considered. The emissions and resource flows saved do not arise in the actual project household, but in the recipient household; however, the savings are attributable to the giving away of leftovers.

Figure 3. Expected material flow changes: give away the leftovers

The challenge of sharing your leftover management skills with others doesn't directly reduce the own households

3.2 Expected effects on resource flows: packaging

The first strategy in the packaging domain for reducing resource flows is to avoid single-use packaging, for example by purchasing food with no packaging or purchasing the same products surrounded with less packaging material. For this reason, material flows are changing in two ways. First, the amount of single-use packaging and the associated amount of waste generated by the disposal of packaging is reduced. However, this is contrasted by the additional effort required to purchase products without packaging, as it still must be carried around somehow. Therefore, this requires reusable packaging. This must first be produced and then prepared for each transport operation to enable transport (e.g. rinsing containers before transporting food). When collecting data, households must be able to specify which reusable containers they have used and which single-use containers they have been able to save as a result. In case there is no reusable container needed for transportation, of course households can also select the option of no further reusable container was needed. Fig. 4 illustrates the change of the material flows according to this behavioural change within the posed challenge.

Figure 4. Expected material flow changes: Avoid packaging

The second packaging behaviour in Fig. 5 considers the reuse of bags, containers, coffee cups or lunch boxes instead of single-use packaging. This behaviour reduces the demand for primary packaging materials and thus the resource flow of these packaging materials. However, there is also a need for producing the reusable packaging alternatives and keeping them usable. For example, the reusable packaging items need to be cleaned or washed after usage in order to use them multiple times. When collecting data, households must be able to specify which reusable containers they have used and which disposable single-use containers they have been able to save as a result.

Figure 5. Expected material flow changes: Reusing (single-use) packaging

The behaviour of avoiding packaging together and buying products in bulk, is shown in Figure 6. By buying in bulk, the amount of packaging material might decrease due to bigger packaging sizes being used. Therefore, the required amount of packaging material per product unit decreases and resource flows can be saved. Households must report which larger packaging sizes they have now purchased and how this has reduced the need for smaller packaging sizes.

Figure 6. Expected material flow changes: Avoid packaging together

3.3 Expected effects on resource flows: textiles

The behaviour of reducing textiles and its respective challenge is shown in Fig. 7. By households refraining from purchasing new clothing, the total amount of textiles required and purchased by individual households decreases. This results in direct savings potential within the same products and substitute products are not required in this context. At the same time, this scenario reduces the amount of waste generated (*ceteris paribus*). To model this scenario, households must be able to estimate which items of clothing they will not purchase as part of this behaviour.

Figure 7. Expected material flow changes: Reduce textile

The purchase of second-hand products does not initially reduce the purchase of new clothing within the household that sells the clothes. However, Fig. 8 shows that this reduces purchases by other households, thereby reducing material flows in third-party households and in total. In this scenario, still the amount of waste generated in the households who are selling items decreases (*ceteris paribus*). Within the challenge of this behaviour, the project households fulfil the role of purchasing households, so they are illustrated as household 2 in Fig. 8. To model this scenario, households must be able to estimate which items of clothing they were purchasing as part of their behaviour.

Figure 8. Expected material flow changes: second hand clothes

Within the behaviour of reusing, repairing and upcycling, the amount of new materials purchased is reduced, which in turn reduces material flows of households. The same applies to the amount of waste generated. However, in order to implement this behaviour, additional effort is required, such as repair materials, which must also be recorded. The data collection process records which products have been repaired or reused and whether and what efforts were necessary to extend the life cycle of the respective product.

Figure 9. Expected material flow changes: reuse, repair, upcycle

3.4 Expected effects on resource flows: electronics

The behaviour of reducing to buy electronics aims to share electronic devices with other households. This reduces the total demand for electronic devices in several households and, proportionally, the material flows that arise within each household. As part of the data collection, households must be able to indicate which devices they shared with other households and to what extent they shared it. Fig. 10 indicates the changes of resource flow connected to this behavioural change.

Figure 10. Expected material flow changes: reduce buying electronics

Within the behaviour of broken electronics shown in Fig. 11, the quantity of newly manufactured products decreases as old devices can be repaired, thereby increasing their service life. The longer service life also reduces the amount of waste generated in households. The implementation of this behaviour is associated with additional costs, such as repair materials, which must also be recorded. The data collection needs to record which products have been repaired and whether and what expenses were necessary to extend the life cycle of the respective product.

Figure 11. Expected material flow changes: broken electronics

The purchase or sale of second-hand electronics reduces the need for new purchases. As shown in Fig. 12, the total resource flows of several households are reduced in total. To model this scenario, households must be able to estimate which electronic devices they have bought or sold on second-hand platforms as part of their behaviour.

Figure 12. Expected material flow changes: reuse electronics

In terms of LCA modelling and data collection, the behaviour of sharing electronics corresponds to the behaviour of reducing electronics. The steps involved are therefore equivalent and Fig. 13 resembles Fig. 10.

Figure 13. Expected material flow changes: share electronics

4. Identifying significant products

The general aim is to record all significant material flows and to make their impact visible through a subsequent LCA. Accordingly, the first step is to develop framework conditions for the materiality of products and then operationalize them on the four domains.

Materiality in the sense of life cycle assessment according to DIN EN ISO standards 14040 and 14044 exists when, on the one hand, larger quantities of materials or significant environmental impacts of certain material flows are to be expected. The product of these two factors could also be used to calculate an expected value for the environmental impact, for example.

Further criteria for the suitability of certain products to be items of the study are that the changes in resource flows are expected to be observed sufficiently during recording period and that the resource flows of the products must be expected to alter through the behavioural changes set.

4.1 Food

In terms of the food domain, we want to include items that:

- can be measured adequately or at least roughly estimated,
- represent typical households' diets,
- are expected to have significant environmental impact, due to their quantity of occurrence or their high EI per unit
- are perishable in the course of the observation time and therefore can be observed adequately

As part of the analysis, statistics were used to determine which foods that meet the above criteria have the highest expected resource flows. In addition, the product lists presented were agreed upon, supplemented and adapted by decision-making groups. Hübsch (2021) identified fruit/vegetables, baked goods and dairy products as particularly important food groups in terms of the dimension of resource flows. In this context we determined the detailed composition of the categories based on consumption volumes. Products that occur particularly frequently are included in the item lists accordingly. The sources of the consumption volumes are German statistics from Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Rural Affairs (BMEL), which are listed in the sources.

However environmental studies as Reinhardt et al. (2020) highlight the importance of animal products in terms of significant EI per unit. The appendix also contains an extension of the list to include literature values with a respective EI. As these are neither country-specific nor do they have a uniform scope that is in line with the project objectives, the modelling of the EI will be included in work package 5.

<i>category</i>	<i>product</i>	<i>unit</i>
Animal products	Pork	kg
	Beef	kg
	Poultry	kg
	Mutton	kg
	Veggy-alternative (wheat-based)	kg
	Veggy-alternative (soy bean-based)	kg
	eggs	kg
seafood	Salmon	kg
	(Alaska) Pollock	kg

	Tuna	kg
	Shrimps	kg
	Other fish (as herring)	kg
	Other seafood (as mussels)	kg
Dairy	Milk	l
	Plant-based milk alternative	l
	Cheese (hard)	kg
	Cheese (fresh)	kg
	Butter	kg
	Yoghurt	kg
	Plant-based yoghurt alternative	kg
	Quark	kg
	Whipped cream	l
Bread / Grain products	White bread / toast	S M L
	Wholegrain bread	S M L
	Whitebread rolls	pieces
	Wholegrain rolls	pieces
	cereals	kg
Fruits	Banana	kg
	Citrus fruits	kg
	Peaches	kg
	Other tropical fruits (as mango, pineapple)	kg
	Apples	kg
	Grapes	kg
	Strawberries	kg
	Other berries	kg
	Other native fruits (as plum, pear, cherry)	kg
vegetables	Potatoes	kg
	Root vegetables (as carrots, beetroot)	kg
	Tomato	kg
	Cucumber	kg
	Onions	kg

	Cabbage	kg
	Beans, peas	kg
	Broccoli, Cauliflower	kg
	Other vegetable as peppers, mushrooms	kg
Cooked meals	Main dish (as animal products with dropdown)	Plates full of meal
	side dish (as carb-containing with dropdown)	
	side dish (as vegetables with dropdown)	

Table 2. List of items: domain of food

4.2 Packaging

In Terms of the packaging domain, we consider the most important packaging sizes and materials. These are shown in Table 3.

<i>category</i>	<i>product</i>	<i>unit</i>
Tin can	Filling mass of 0,2 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces
Tetra pak	Filling volume of 1 l	pieces
	Filling volume of 2 l	pieces
Cups (e.g. for yoghurt; PP)	Filling mass of 0,2 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces
Glass container	Filling mass of 0,2 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces
Plastic bags (PP or PE)	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces
PET trays	Filling mass of 0,2 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces
PET trays with PE film	Filling mass of 0,2 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces
Paper / Card board	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces

	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 5 kg	pieces
	Filling mass of 10 kg	pieces

Table 3. List of items: domain of packaging

4.3 Textiles

In terms of the textiles domain, we consider the most important types of clothing as well as the most important fabrics regarding EI and occurrence. The resulting items and products are shown in Table 4.

<i>category</i>	<i>product</i>	<i>unit</i>
cotton	T-shirt	pieces
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces
	Socks	pieces
	Coat	pieces
	Slip	pieces
	Trousers	pieces
	skirt	pieces
	Dress	pieces
	Pyjama	pieces
	sweatpants	pieces
Denim	T-shirt	pieces
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces
	Socks	pieces
	Coat	pieces
	Slip	pieces
	Trousers	pieces
	skirt	pieces
	Dress	pieces
	Pyjama	pieces
	sweatpants	pieces
Wool	T-shirt	pieces
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces
	Socks	pieces

	Coat	pieces
	Slip	pieces
	Trousers	pieces
	skirt	pieces
	Dress	pieces
	Pyjama	pieces
	sweatpants	pieces
Silk	T-shirt	pieces
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces
	Socks	pieces
	Coat	pieces
	Slip	pieces
	Trousers	pieces
	skirt	pieces
	Dress	pieces
	Pyjama	pieces
	sweatpants	pieces
polyester	T-shirt	pieces
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces
	Socks	pieces
	Coat	pieces
	Slip	pieces
	Trousers	pieces
	skirt	pieces
	Dress	pieces
	Pyjama	pieces
	sweatpants	pieces
nylon	T-shirt	pieces
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces
	Socks	pieces
	Coat	pieces
	Slip	pieces

	Trousers	pieces
	skirt	pieces
	Dress	pieces
	Pyjama	pieces
	sweatpants	pieces
Elastane	T-shirt	pieces
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces
	Socks	pieces
	Coat	pieces
	Slip	pieces
	Trousers	pieces
	skirt	pieces
	Dress	pieces
	Pyjama	pieces
	sweatpants	pieces
Blends	T-shirt	pieces
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces
	Socks	pieces
	Coat	pieces
	Slip	pieces
	Trousers	pieces
	skirt	pieces
	Dress	pieces
	Pyjama	pieces
	sweatpants	pieces

Table 4. List of items: domain of textiles

4.4 Electronics

With regard to the electronics domain, there are significantly less products to model, therefore, the focus of data gathering is on collecting the items that were shared or repaired. Therefore, the list consists of the most common devices that are

possessed by households and that fit in line with the requirements of the challenges (e.g. shareable or repairable).

<i>category</i>	<i>product</i>	<i>unit</i>
Large appliances	fridge / freezer	pieces
	Washing machine	pieces
	Dryer	pieces
	Oven	pieces
	dishwasher	pieces
Medium-size appliances	Microwave	pieces
	(filter) coffee machine	pieces
	Fully automated coffee machine	pieces
	Toaster	pieces
	Vacuum cleaner	pieces
	Laptop	pieces
Small appliances	Handheld vacuum cleaner	pieces
	Hair dryer	pieces
	Mixer	pieces
	Mobile phone	pieces
	tablet	pieces
	Electric tooth brush	pieces
	Electric shaver	pieces

Table 5. List of items: domain of electronics

5. Quantification of resource savings by using CircleUp app

Due to the high effort that would be required for households to record the status quo and the post-challenge state, the project team as a whole has agreed to obtain LCA-related data exclusively via the app. In this course, the effort required for households to record LCA-relevant savings should be kept to a minimum level of time. Savings can be determined, for example, by conducting a baseline survey of resource flows and a survey of resource flows during or after the challenges have been carried out. This raises several practical problems (the order in which they are listed does not reflect the importance of the argument):

1. extent of the status quo assessment – as part of the assessment, all household resource flows would have to be recorded in advance. This would involve a great deal of effort on the participating households. The project team decided that this would not be in the interests of households and would not be compatible with the objectives of the project.
2. Carrying out the assessment after each individual challenge - The assessment would have to be carried out in full (within the respective domain) after each challenge. With four domains and several behavioural changes in each case, the effort involved here is also anything but insignificant.
3. Attributability to specific challenges – simply surveying the pre-challenge and post-challenge situations does not provide certainty as to whether the challenge was the reason for a possible change in resource flows.

It is therefore planned to assess the savings potential of households for each challenge individually. For each challenge, the households are asked to quantify their changes of resource flows. The households are free how often and when to fill in their savings, however they are just asked once and not asked to quantify an ex-ante and an ex-post situation. . But still, there are some issues to consider when gathering data for potential savings. Since this self-reported data of households could be incomplete and / or biased, it is compared - where possible - with data from the automated waste data analysis and checked for plausibility. Therefore, the data from the waste bins is not directly included in the calculations as it does not differentiate sufficiently between the different types of waste generated and respectively the products saved. The smart bin data will be used for plausibility check to ckeck whether the actual resource reductions of waste are in lign with the expected changes due to the quantified savings within the list. If there is a significant difference between expected waste and smart bin data, there is a need for further investigation of the incident, e.g. by a consultant to check what the reasons were and what the consequences for modelling are.

The lists of products considered in the previous chapter are to be queried within the app. As part of the challenges, households are asked in a separate section with individual questions what savings they were able to achieve. The corresponding questions for each behaviour are shown in table 6.

<i>Behaviour</i>		<i>Question to assess savings</i>
Food	Plan purchases to avoid food waste	In the course of the challenge, I reduced my food purchases by planning. Compared to my ordinary purchases, I bought fewer of the following products:
	Reuse leftovers	In the course of the challenge, I reused the leftover food that I would otherwise have thrown away:
	Give away leftovers	1. In the course of the challenge, I passed on the following foods to my friends, neighbours and XY.
	Share your leftover management skills with others	[will not be considered in terms of LCA]
Packaging	Avoid packaging (focus on refuse, reduce)	1. In the course of the challenge, I have taken my own reusable bag with me and therefore saved the following packagings: 2. To be able to avoid single-use packaging, I used the following reusable container:
	Reuse packaging	1. In the course of the challenge, I have avoided the following single-use packaging by reusing packagings. 2. To be able to avoid single-use packaging, I used the following reusable containers:
	Avoid packaging together	1. In the course of the challenge, I have purchased the following big-size packagings: 2. By purchasing big-size packaging, I could save the following medium-size and small-size packagings:
Textiles	reduce textiles	In the course of the challenge, I have decided not to buy excessive amounts of clothing. this has prevented me from buying the following clothes:
	Buy second hand	In the course of the challenge, I have bought secondhand clothes instead of brand-new ones:
	Reuse, repair, upcycle	1. In the course of the challenge, I have repaired a clothing item that was damaged:

		2. In the course of repairing my item, I used the following materials:
Electronics	Reduce buying electronics	1. In the course of the challenge, I didn't buy the following electrical devices as I was sharing it with other households in the course of a professional sharing service model or private lending 2. In the course of the challenge, I have given an electronic device to someone else
	broken electronics	1. In the course of the challenge, I have repaired the following electrical device: 2. In the course of repairing my item, I used the following materials:
	Reuse electronics	In the course of the challenge, I have bought the following second-hand electronic device instead of a new one
	share electronics	In the course of the challenge, I have shared an electronic device with someone else

Table 6. Quantifying behavioural changes

Figure 14. shows mock-up ideas to display within the CircleUp app that were used during the development of the query. These are explicitly not clips from the app.

Figure 14. Mock-Up of data gathering within the app

Households are asked to add their quantities of savings. Entering the lists must be convenient, simple and error-proof for households. Since the item lists contain quite

a large number of items and yet need to be clearly structured for households, they are divided into the categories already shown in the tables. In the case of the food domain and the electronics domain, the app could feature a drop-down menu in which households can select and quantify the relevant items. In the case of the packaging and textiles domains, drop-down menus are also suitable in principle, but kits in which households can configure their own products are probably even more suitable here. To illustrate this using the example of textiles: in this case, households could select that they have repaired a pair of trousers made of cotton. The type of clothing (trousers) would be one variable to be selected, the material (cotton) the other variable.

6. Literature

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Appendix A

The tables in the appendix show the products that households report as part of the savings potential assessment. To give households direct feedback on a rough estimate of impact saving their actions can achieve, the tables also include the emission factor (in kg) and weight per unit. This allows the potential savings per unit to be calculated and reported directly to households when they enter their savings. It should be noted that the values are based on existing literature, database values or estimates of product groups. The literature often gives ranges of values, as the results strongly vary depending on the modelling (e.g. allocation differences) or different goals and scopes of the studies. In this case, a value in the middle of the range is shown in the table. The same applies to the conversion factors. The weight per unit/product may vary depending on the circumstances of the item. Take textiles, for example: depending on the size and thickness of the garment, the weight within a product may also vary within a certain range. Here, too, an average value is selected from a range of weights. Since there is no common scope, framework conditions and system boundaries for emission factors and weights among all the studies, and since there may be country-specific differences in both respects, a separate modelling with common system boundaries, assumptions and weight values is required for a more precise project-related evaluation in WP 5.

<i>category</i>	<i>product</i>	<i>unit</i>	<i>Weight per unit</i>	<i>EI (CO2)</i>	<i>source</i>
Animal products	Pork	kg	-	4	Reinhardt et al. (2020); Møller & Samsonstuen (2024)
	Beef	kg	-	18	
	Poultry	kg	-	3	

	Mutton	kg	-	28	Møller & Samsonstuen (2024)
	Veggy-alternative (wheat-based)	kg	-	2,5	Reinhardt et al. (2020)
	Veggy-alternative (soy bean-based)	kg	-	1	
	eggs	kg	-	3	
seafood	Salmon	kg	-	4	Reinhardt et al. (2020)
	(Alaska) Pollock	kg	-	4,5	
	Tuna	kg	-	9	
	Shrimps	kg	-	12	
	Other fish (as herring)	kg	-	5,1	
	Other seafood (as mussels)	kg	-	4,5	
Dairy	Milk	l		1,4	Nilsson et al. (2010); Reinhardt et al. (2020); De Lima Casseres Dos Santos et al. (2022)
	Plant-based milk alternative	l		0,4	
	Cheese (hard)	kg	-	9	
	Cheese (fresh)	kg	-	6	
	Butter	kg	-	12	
	Yoghurt	kg	-	1,9	
	Plant-based yoghurt alternative	kg	-	0,6	
	Quark	kg	-	4	
	Whipped cream	l		5	
Bread / Grain	White bread / toast	S M L	0,5 0,75 1	0,75	Hildersten et al. (2025);
	Wholegrain bread	S M L	0,5 0,75 1	0,65	Reinhardt et al. (2020)
	Whitebread rolls	pieces	0,05 kg	0,75	
	Wholegrain rolls	pieces	0,05 kg	0,65	

	cereals	kg	-	0,6	
Fruits	Banana	kg	-	0,6	Reinhardt et al. (2020)
	Citrus fruits	kg	-	0,3	
	Peaches	kg	-	0,6	
	Other tropical fruits (as mango, pineapple)	kg	-	0,5*	
	Apples	kg	-	0,3	Reinhardt et al. (2020)
	Grapes	kg	-	0,4	
	Strawberries	kg	-	0,3	
	Other berries	kg	-	0,3**	
	Other native fruits (as plum, pear, cherry)	kg	-	0,4**	
	vegetables	Potatoes	kg	-	0,2
Root vegetables (as carrots, beetroot)		kg	-	0,2	
Tomato		kg	-	0,8	
Cucumber		kg	-	0,3	
Onions		kg	-	0,2	
Cabbage		kg	-	0,1	
Beans, peas		kg	-	0,8	
Broccoli, Cauliflower		kg	-	0,4	
Other vegetable as peppers, mushrooms		kg	-	0,4***	
Cooked meals	Main dish (as animal products with dropdown)	Plates full of meal			

	side dish (as carb-containing with dropdown)				
	side dish (as vegetables with dropdown)				

Table 7. List of items: domain of food and EI

* Estimated values within the range of other values

** Estimated values within the range of other values

*** Estimated values within the range of other values

<i>category</i>	<i>product</i>	<i>unit</i>	<i>Weight per unit</i>	<i>EI (CO2) per kg</i>	<i>source</i>
Tin can	Filling mass of 0,2 kg	pieces	0,03 kg	2,2	Eslami et al. (2025)
	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces	0,05 kg		
	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces	0,075 kg		
Tetra pak	Filling volume of 1 l	pieces	0,035 kg	2,8	Schlecht et al. (2019)
	Filling volume of 2 l	pieces	0,068 kg		
Cups (e.g. for yoghurt; PP)	Filling mass of 0,2 kg	pieces	0,01 kg	1,8	Schlecht et al. (2019)
	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces	0,02 kg		
	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces	0,03 kg		
Glass container	Filling mass of 0,2 kg	pieces	0,125 kg	1,3	Eslami et al. (2025)
	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces	0,25 kg		
	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces	0,5 kg		
	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces	0,007 kg	2	

Plastic bags (PP or PE)	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces	0,01 kg		Franklin Associates (2018)
PET trays	Filling mass of 0,2 kg	pieces	0,011 kg	3	
	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces	0,020 kg		
	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces	0,032 kg		
PET trays with PE film	Filling mass of 0,2 kg	pieces	0,014 kg	2,8	
	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces	0,025 kg		
	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces	0,042 kg		
Paper / Card board	Filling mass of 0,5 kg	pieces	0,010 kg	1	NCASI (2020)
	Filling mass of 1 kg	pieces	0,017 kg		
	Filling mass of 5 kg	pieces	0,030 kg		
	Filling mass of 10 kg	pieces	0,350 kg		

Table 8. List of items: domain of packaging and EI

<i>category</i>	<i>product</i>	<i>unit</i>	<i>Weight per unit</i>	<i>EI (CO2) per kg</i>	<i>source</i>
cotton	T-shirt	pieces	0,15 kg	22	Van der Velden et al. (2013)
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces	0,5 kg		
	Socks	pieces	0,065 kg		
	Coat	pieces	1,2 kg		
	Slip	pieces	0,05 kg		

	Trousers	pieces	0,5 kg		
	skirt	pieces	0,3 kg		
	Dress	pieces	0,3 kg		
	Pyjama	pieces	0,4 kg		
	sweatpants	pieces	0,4 kg		
Denim	T-shirt	pieces	0,25 kg	33	Levi Strauss & CO (2015)
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces	0,75 kg		
	Socks	pieces	(-)		
	Coat	pieces	1,6 kg		
	Slip	pieces	(-)		
	Trousers	pieces	0,8 kg		
	skirt	pieces	0,55 kg		
	Dress	pieces	0,65 kg		
	Pyjama	pieces	0,7 kg		
	sweatpants	pieces	0,7 kg		
Wool	T-shirt	pieces	0,18 kg	20	Henry et al. (2015); Bianco et al. (2023)
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces	0,65 kg		
	Socks	pieces	0,08 kg		
	Coat	pieces	1,7 kg		
	Slip	pieces	0,065 kg		
	Trousers	pieces	0,65 kg		
	skirt	pieces	0,5 kg		
	Dress	pieces	0,65 kg		
	Pyjama	pieces	0,5 kg		
	sweatpants	pieces	0,6 kg		
Silk	T-shirt	pieces	0,1 kg	51,5	Astudillo et al. (2015)
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces	0,32 kg		
	Socks	pieces	0,03 kg		
	Coat	pieces	0,6 kg		
	Slip	pieces	0,35 kg		
	Trousers	pieces	0,2 kg		

	skirt	pieces	0,2 kg		
	Dress	pieces	0,25 kg		
	Pyjama	pieces	0,25 kg		
	sweatpants	pieces	0,2 kg		
polyester	T-shirt	pieces	0,12 kg	15	Van der Velden et al. (2013)
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces	0,4 kg		
	Socks	pieces	0,05 kg		
	Coat	pieces	0,9 kg		
	Slip	pieces	0,04 kg		
	Trousers	pieces	0,4 kg		
	skirt	pieces	0,25 kg		
	Dress	pieces	0,3 kg		
	Pyjama	pieces	0,35 kg		
	sweatpants	pieces	0,35 kg		
nylon	T-shirt	pieces	0,11 kg	20	Van der Velden et al. (2013)
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces	0,35 kg		
	Socks	pieces	0,035 kg		
	Coat	pieces	0,6 kg		
	Slip	pieces	0,03 kg		
	Trousers	pieces	0,3 kg		
	skirt	pieces	0,2 kg		
	Dress	pieces	0,3 kg		
	Pyjama	pieces	0,25 kg		
	sweatpants	pieces	0,3 kg		
Elastane	T-shirt	pieces	0,13 kg	18	Van der Velden et al. (2013)
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces	0,4 kg		
	Socks	pieces	0,04 kg		
	Coat	pieces	0,6 kg		
	Slip	pieces	0,03 kg		
	Trousers	pieces	0,3 kg		
	skirt	pieces	0,2 kg		

	Dress	pieces	0,3 kg		
	Pyjama	pieces	0,3 kg		
	sweatpants	pieces	0,3 kg		
Blends	T-shirt	pieces	0,15 kg	12,5	Tekin et al. (2024)
	Jumper / hoodie	pieces	0,45 kg		
	Socks	pieces	0,055 kg		
	Coat	pieces	1,2 kg		
	Slip	pieces	0,045 kg		
	Trousers	pieces	0,55 kg		
	skirt	pieces	0,3 kg		
	Dress	pieces	0,35 kg		
	Pyjama	pieces	0,4 kg		
	sweatpants	pieces	0,45 kg		

Table 9. List of items: domain of textiles and EI

<i>category</i>	<i>product</i>	<i>unit</i>	<i>Weight per unit</i>	<i>EI (CO2) per kg</i>	<i>source</i>
Large appliances	Washing machine	pieces	65 kg	8	Alejandro et al. (2022)
	Dryer	pieces	50 kg		
	Oven	pieces	40 kg		
	dishwasher	pieces	45 kg		
Medium-size appliances	Microwave	pieces	12 kg	6,5	Hischier et al. (2020) Prakash et al. (2015)
	(filter) coffee machine	pieces	3 kg		
	Fully automatic coffee machine	pieces	10 kg		
	Toaster	pieces	1,5 kg		
	Vacuum cleaner	pieces	6 kg		
	Laptop	pieces	2 kg		
Small appliances	Handheld vacuum cleaner	pieces	1,5 kg	5,5	

	Hair dryer	pieces	1 kg		
	Mixer	pieces	1 kg		
	Mobile phone	pieces	0,2 kg		
	Tablet	pieces	0,4 kg		
	Electric tooth brush	pieces	0,15 kg		
	Electric shaver	pieces	0,3 kg		

Table 10. List of items: domain of electronics and EI